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RECORDS OF MAMMALS FROM THE MEXICAN STATE OF
SAN LUIS POTOSI

By WALTER W. DALQUEST

A number of species of neotropical mammals seem to find their northern limits of distribution in the State of San Luis Potosí, México. Although a detailed survey of the distribution of the mammals in that state is now being sponsored by the Louisiana State University Museum of Zoology, the final report will not be completed for some time. It appears advisable, therefore, to make immediately available certain distributional and taxonomic information, based on the material already assembled.

The rather large collection of mammals on which this report is based was made entirely by personnel connected with the various ornithological expeditions of the Louisiana State University Museum of Zoology since August, 1946. The mammal material was taken incidentally to the collecting of birds. The majority of the specimens were secured by Charles Shaw, and it is a pleasure to name in this report a new subspecies of squirrel in recognition of his contribution to mammalogy. Much credit is also due Robert J. Newman who, as leader of the several expeditions, directed attention to the collection of mammals as well as other vertebrates. Many valuable specimens were taken by Marcella Newman and Herbert Stern, and a smaller number by George H. Lowery, Jr., and Prentiss D. Lewis. Dyfrig McH. Forbes of Potrero Viejo, Veracruz, México, obtained for the museum collection, and for immediate use in this report, topotypical specimens of *Artibeus lituratus palmarum* at Port of Spain, Trinidad, British West Indies. For the loan of comparative material and help in other ways, I am indebted to William B. Davis, Agricultural and

Mechanical College of Texas; Stanley P. Young, United States Fish and Wildlife Service; Henry W. Setzer, United States National Museum; and George G. Goodwin, American Museum of Natural History.

All measurements listed in the following accounts are in millimeters, and unless otherwise noted all localities are in the State of San Luis Potosí. The approximate latitude and longitude of each of the localities in San Luis Potosí mentioned in the text are as follows: Apetsco or Rancho Apetsco, 21° 24', 99° 02'; Cerro Campanario, 21° 54', 100° 25'; Cerro Conejo, 21° 24', 99° 06'; Cerro Miramar, 21° 24', 99° 02'; City of San Luis Potosí, 22° 10', 100° 58'; El Salto, 22° 36', 99° 24'; Pendencia, 22° 32', 99° 35'; Rancho Miramar Grande, 21° 25', 99° 05'; Rancho San Francisco, 22° 07', 100° 37'; Tamazunchale, 21° 16', 98° 48'; Tamuín, 21° 59', 98° 46'; Valles or Ciudad Valles, 21° 58', 99° 02'; Villar, 22° 32', 100° 27'; Xilitla, 21° 23', 99° 01'.

PHILANDER OPOSSUM PALLIDUS (Allen)

FOUR-EYED OPOSSUM

Metachirus fuscogriseus pallidus Allen, Bull. Amer. Mus. Nat. Hist., 14, 1901: 215. (Orizaba, Veracruz, México.)

Previously this small marsupial has been recorded northward only to central Veracruz. There are two specimens in the collection of the Louisiana State University Museum of Zoology: one from Xilitla and one from Valles. Both seem to be typical of the subspecies *pallidus*, described from central Veracruz.

CAROLLIA PERSPICILLATA AZTECA Saussure

SHORT-TAILED BAT

Carollia azteca Saussure, Revue et Magasin de Zool., ser. 2, 12, 1860: 480. (Peréz, Veracruz, México, by restriction.)

This species has been recorded by Hahn (1907: 32) from the "Hot, humid regions of southern Mexico and Central America," but he makes no specific mention of its occurrence farther north than central Veracruz. There are twelve specimens, skins with skulls, in the collection from a cave located ten kilometers north and three kilometers east of the town of Xilitla. The specimens are all of the gray phase, like *azteca* from central Veracruz, and lack the reddish color found often in individuals of this species from Central America.

ARTIBEUS LITURATUS PALMARUM Allen and Chapman

TRINIDAD FRUIT BAT

Artibeus palmarum Allen and Chapman, Bull. Amer. Mus. Nat. Hist., 9, 1897: 16. (Trinidad, British West Indies.)

This species has been recorded in Mexico by Andersen (1908: 278) from Oaxaca, Veracruz, and Jalisco (=Nayarit). There are seven specimens in the collection: five from ten kilometers north and three kilometers east of Xilitla, one from Xilitla, and another from one mile north of Tamazunchale. Two of these bats are young animals. The mean cranial measurements for three adult males and two adult females are, respectively: greatest length of skull, 30.1, 30.0; condylobasal length, 27.1, 26.9; length of tooth row, entire, 11.6, 11.6; post-palatal length (from posterior border of palate to anterior lip of foramen magnum), 9.6, 9.6; zygomatic breadth, 18.9, 18.7; interorbital breadth, 6.8, 6.7; alveolar breadth across upper second molars, 13.5, 13.5; mastoid breadth, 16.2, 16.2.

Compared with topotypes of *A. l. palmarum* from Port of Spain, Trinidad, the material from San Luis Potosí is similar in size and in cranial characters, but the facial stripes are markedly and uniformly shorter and more obscure, and in color are more brownish and less white. The color of the upper parts of the material from Mexico is darker and slightly richer in tone.

DIPHYLLA ECAUDATA CENTRALIS Thomas

HAIRY-LEGGED VAMPIRE

Diphylla centralis Thomas, Ann. and Mag. Nat. Hist., 11 (7), 1903: 378. (Boquete, Chiriquí, Panamá.)

Previous to 1947, this species was known only from as far north as southern Mexico. In that year, Dalquest and Hall (1947: 315) reported specimens from central Veracruz and Hidalgo. There are eleven specimens of this rare bat in the collection from San Luis Potosí, all taken in a cave located ten kilometers north and three kilometers east of Xilitla. One specimen is a young female, nearly full grown on March 10, 1947. The series includes also seven adult males and three adult females, the mean cranial measurements for which are, respectively: greatest length of skull, 23.5, 23.8; condylobasal length, 20.8, 21.1; palatal length, 6.5, 6.5; post-palatal length, 10.9, 11.4; zygomatic breadth, 12.6, 13.0; interorbital breadth, 7.2, 7.3; braincase breadth, 11.6, 11.6; mastoid breadth,

12.1, 12.3. Three females, taken on March 10, 1947, each held a single fetus.

SYLVILAGUS GABBI TRUEI (Allen)

JUNGLE RABBIT

Lepus truei Allen, Bull. Amer. Mus. Nat. Hist., 3, 1890: 192. (Mirador, Veracruz, México.)

This rabbit has been recorded by Nelson (1909: 264) northward only as far as central Veracruz and adjacent parts of Puebla. An adult female in the collection was taken at Rancho Apetsco, near Xilitla, and marks a considerable northward extension of range for the species.

SCIURUS OCULATUS SHAWI new subspecies

SPECTACLED SQUIRREL

Type.—Adult female, skin and skull; no. 2842, Louisiana State University Museum of Zoology; Rancho San Francisco, 38 kilometers east-southeast of the City of San Luis Potosí, San Luis Potosí, México; obtained on March 30, 1947 by Charles Shaw; original number M219.

Range.—The mountain forests of the southern and central parts of the State of San Luis Potosí, México.

Diagnosis.—A large tree squirrel; a single upper premolar on each side; total length of adult more than 500 millimeters; fur long and relatively soft; upper parts uniform "salt-and-pepper" gray, save for buffy eye ring and post-auricular patch; feet and under parts rich buff; tail above black and heavily frosted with white, especially along edges; under side of tail with median area yellowish-brown, followed by a narrow black band, and edged with a broad white band.

Comparisons.—*Sciurus oculatus shawi* differs from *Sciurus oculatus oculatus* Peters¹ in lacking the stripe along the back. This stripe varies, in the subspecies *oculatus*, from a deep, black band to a blackish wash, but is always present. In *shawi* there is no trace of a dark wash on the back. From *Sciurus oculatus tolucae* Nelson,² *shawi* differs, as it does from *oculatus*, in lacking the blackish dorsal stripe, and in addition, *shawi* is rich buff rather than whitish beneath. From *Sciurus alleni* Nelson,³ the

¹ *Sciurus oculatus* Peters, Monatsber. k. preuss. Akad. Wissensch., Berlin, 1863: 653. (Las Vigas, Veracruz, México.)

² *Sciurus oculatus tolucae* Nelson, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 12, 1898: 148. (Volcán de Toluca, State of México, México.)

³ *Sciurus alleni* Nelson, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 12, 1898: 147. (Monterrey, Nuevo León, México.)

only species with which *Sciurus oculatus shawi* might be confused, *shawi* differs in having buffy, rather than brownish or whitish, feet; in having distinct, buffy post-auricular patches; and in having deep buffy under parts rather than pure white under parts. In *Sciurus alleni* the post-auricular patches are usually absent, and when present, consist of a tiny area where the fur is slightly shorter and grayer than on the surrounding part of the head.

Remarks.—When E. W. Nelson (1899) revised the tree squirrels of Mexico and Central America, he had available fifty-three specimens of *Sciurus oculatus*, seven of which he referred to the subspecies *Sciurus oculatus tolucae*. He remarked (*op. cit.*) that of the forty-six specimens of *oculatus* all have the back black or washed with black, except that "two specimens from Villar, San Luis Potosí, in worn summer pelage, differ in being uniform gray on the back, scarcely darker along the median line, but they agree with the Pinal de Amoles specimens in the rich, buffy underparts." The four specimens in our collection all agree with the description of the two specimens examined by Nelson long ago. It is therefore obvious that *Sciurus oculatus shawi* is a strongly-marked subspecies, with a geographic range along the northern border of the general range of the species as a whole.

The nearest relative of *Sciurus oculatus* is *Sciurus alleni*. This species ranges immediately to the north of *Sciurus oculatus shawi*. The principal differences between *oculatus* and *alleni* are the smaller size and white under parts of *alleni*. The skulls of the two species are so similar that, as pointed out by Nelson (*op. cit.*, p. 92), the skulls of *alleni* "are only distinguishable from those of *S. oculatus* by their smaller size." Specimens of *alleni* from San Luis Potosí are larger than specimens from Nuevo León and Coahuila, and this increase in size might be considered as an approach to *oculatus*. The uniform gray back of *Sciurus oculatus shawi* might be regarded as a tendency toward *alleni*. There are, however, two differences of considerable magnitude between the two species, namely, the white, as contrasted with the buffy, belly, and the near or complete absence of post-auricular patches in *alleni*. These two characters show no intergradation. The specimens examined by Nelson from Villar were taken only ninety kilometers west of Penedencia, where the field party from the Museum of Zoology obtained specimens of *alleni*. Because the two forms occur close together but retain certain differences, they are best regarded as full species. Further work in the State of San Luis Potosí

should show either that the two forms intergrade, and thus are conspecific, or that the two forms occur together without interbreeding, and thus are full species. Probably the latter situation will be found to be the case.

Measurements.—The mean external and cranial measurements of three adult females, two from the type locality and one from Cerro Campanario, are: total length, 508; length of tail, 256; length of hind foot, 68; greatest length of skull, 62.9; condylobasal length, 55.9; alveolar length of maxillary tooth row, 11.2; length of diastema, 15.7; postpalatal length, 21.4; zygomatic breadth, 36.5; interorbital breadth, 20.2; mastoid breadth, 25.4; breadth across upper second molars, 14.3.

Figure 1. Distribution of the races of *Sciurus oculatus*. The localities of record, except those based on L.S.U.M.Z. specimens, are from Nelson (1899), and are listed from north to south and from west to east, within the range of each subspecies. Horizontal lines, *SCIURUS OCVLATUS SHAWI*—*San Luis Potosí*: Villar; Rancho San Francisco (LSUMZ); Cerro Campanario (LSUMZ); Cerro Conejo (LSUMZ). Stippled, *SCIURUS OCVLATUS OCVLATUS*—*Quevetaro*: Pinal de Amoles. *Hidalgo*: Encarnacion; Real del Monte; Tulancingo. *Veracruz*: Las Vigas; Cofre de Perote. *Puebla*: Mount Orizaba. Cross hatching, *SCIURUS OCVLATUS TOLUCAE*—*Guanajuato*: Guanajuato City. *Hidalgo*: Tequisquiapan. *México*: Volcán de Toluca.

Specimens examined.—Four, from: Rancho San Francisco [38 km. ESE City of San Luis Potosí], 2; vicinity of Cerro Conejo at Llano de Garzas [ca. 11 km. NW Xilitla], 6800 ft., 1; Cerro Campanario [65 km. SE City of San Luis Potosí], 7500 ft., 1.

ORYZOMYS FULVESCENS FULVESCENS (Saussure)

PYGMY RICE RAT

H[esperomys] fulvescens Saussure, Revue et Magasin de Zool., ser. 2, 12, 1860: 102. (Orizaba, Veracruz, by fixation.)

Two specimens of this mouse were obtained: one at Xilitla and one at three kilometers west of Tamuín. Both are referable to this subspecies, described from central Veracruz, rather than to *Oryzomys fulvescens engraciae*,* described from Tamaulipas. Goldman (1918: 91) referred a specimen from Alta Mira, Tamaulipas, to *fulvescens*, and Osgood (*loc. cit.*) considered the same specimen to be intermediate between *fulvescens* and *engraciae*. The present specimens from San Luis Potosí indicate that the range of typical *fulvescens* extends northward to eastern San Luis Potosí, and probably to southern Tamaulipas as well. Intergradation with *engraciae* must take place still farther to the north.

REITHRODONTOMYS MEXICANUS GOLDMANI Merriam

MEXICAN HARVEST MOUSE

Reithrodontomys goldmani Merriam, Proc. Washington Acad. Sci., 3, 1901: 552. (Metlatoyuca, Puebla. Merriam gives "Melaltoyucca," but this seems to be an error. Modern maps use the name first listed here.)

This species has previously been known from central Veracruz and adjacent parts of Puebla and southward. The five specimens from San Luis Potosí, all taken at Xilitla, mark a northward extension of range for the species.

Howell (1914: 72) states that *goldmani* is smaller and paler than *mexicanus*. The type locality of *mexicanus* is cited as the "Mountains of Veracruz," and probably should be restricted to the vicinity of Mirador, where Saussure is known to have lived and worked. The type locality of *goldmani* is in the same mountain range (any restricted type locality chosen for *mexicanus* will also be in the same mountain range) and only

* *Oryzomys fulvescens engraciae* Osgood, Jour. Mamm., 26, 1945: 300. (Hacienda Santa Engracia, Ciudad Victoria, Tamaulipas.)

115 miles distant from Mirador. Our specimens from San Luis Potosí are large and rich in color. It seems probable, however, that *goldmani* will be shown to be only a synonym of *mexicanus*.

PEROMYSCUS MEXICANUS MEXICANUS (Saussure)

MEXICAN DEER MOUSE

H[esperomys] mexicanus Saussure, Revue et Magasin de Zool., ser. 2, 12, 1860: 103. (Restricted to Mirador, Veracruz, by Osgood, 1909, p. 199. For systematic reasons, it would be better to modify the restriction to ten kilometers east of Mirador.)

Four adult specimens of this species are available from Xilitla. The Mexican Deer Mouse has not previously been recorded from farther north than central Veracruz and Puebla (Osgood, 1909: 202). Our material is, somewhat surprisingly, referable to the subspecies *mexicanus*, the relatively small, pale race, found on the coastal plain of Veracruz, rather than the larger, darker subspecies, *totontopecus*,⁵ which occurs in the higher areas to the west of the range of *mexicanus*.

PEROMYSCUS LATIROSTRIS new species

BROAD-NOSED DEER MOUSE

Type.—Adult male, skin and skull; no. 3051, Louisiana State University Museum of Zoology; Apetsco, near Xilitla, elevation 2700 feet, San Luis Potosí, México; obtained on July 3, 1947, by Marcella Newman; original number M40.

Range.—Known only from a few localities near the type locality, from an elevation of 2000 to 6000 feet, in southeastern San Luis Potosí.

Diagnosis.—A large Deer Mouse, exceeded in size only by the largest members of the genus *Peromyscus*; general proportions and color pattern as in other members of the genus; teeth large and heavy, with strongly-developed outer accessory cusps on the first and second molars; skull large but without beading or ridges on margin of interorbital area; rostrum large and wide with almost parallel sides; tail bicolored.

Comparisons.—Compared with *Peromyscus thomasi* Merriam⁶ and *Peromyscus nelsoni* Merriam,⁷ *Peromyscus latirostris* differs in slightly

⁵*Peromyscus mexicanus totontopecus* Merriam, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 12, 1898: 120. (Totontopec, Oaxaca, México.)

⁶*Peromyscus (Megadontomys) thomasi* Merriam, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 12, 1898: 116. (Mountains near Chilpancingo, Guerrero, México.)

⁷*Peromyscus (Megadontomys) nelsoni* Merriam, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 12, 1898: 116. (Jico, Veracruz, México.)

smaller average size of skull, smaller external measurements, much wider, heavier rostrum with greatly expanded nasals and premaxillae, and smooth, unbeaded interorbital border. Cranially, most specimens of *latirostris* are smaller than specimens of *thomasi* and *nelsoni* of similar age, but the largest skulls of adult *latirostris* are larger than the smallest skulls of adult *thomasi*. There is no overlapping in external measurements, except in the length of the hind foot. In that measurement, large examples of *latirostris* exceed or equal small *thomasi*. In other external measurements, *thomasi* and *nelsoni* are uniformly larger than *latirostris*.

Compared with *Peromyscus fuvvus* Allen and Chapman⁸ *latirostris* differs in its larger size, paler (brownier) color, and more expanded rostrum.

Remarks.—The differences between the subgenera *Peromyscus* and *Megadontomys* are quantitative. *Megadontomys* differs from *Peromyscus* principally in the larger size of the species included, and the more strongly developed accessory cusps on the distal surfaces of the first and second molars. These accessory cusps are rather poorly developed in most members of the subgenus *Peromyscus*. Some members of the subgenus *Peromyscus* are larger than the smaller members of the subgenus *Megadontomys*.

Peromyscus fuvvus is generally placed in the subgenus *Peromyscus* although it has rather well-developed accessory cusps on the first and second molars, and is of relatively large size. It constitutes a form intermediate in characters between the two subgenera.

Peromyscus latirostris represents a step farther in the direction of the subgenus *Megadontomys*. It is nearly as large as certain representatives of the subgenus *Megadontomys*, and has the accessory cusps equally well developed. In general nature of the pelage, *fuvvus*, *latirostris*, *nelsoni*, and *thomasi* are quite similar. In all four species the fur is short, dense, and rather woolly. The two subgenera, *Peromyscus* and *Megadontomys*, are but poorly characterized at best. Nor does the subgenus *Megadontomys* serve any convenient function in dividing the genus *Peromyscus*, for only four species are currently placed in the subgenus *Megadontomys*. It would seem best to abandon the subgenus *Megadontomys* entirely.

⁸ *Peromyscus fuvvus* Allen and Chapman, Bull. Amer. Mus. Nat. Hist., 9, 1897: 201. (Jalapa, Veracruz, México.)

Figure 2. Skulls of adult males of *Peromyscus thomasi*, left; *Peromyscus latirostris*, center; *Peromyscus furvus*, right. x 1.5.

Among the mice of the genus *Peromyscus*, the species *furvus* is noteworthy in the great expansion of the nasals anteriorly. In *latirostris*, this expansion is carried to an extreme degree, so that the sides of the rostrum are almost parallel. In other respects also, *latirostris* is more like *furvus* than it is like any other known species. Certainly it is more closely related to *furvus* than it is to *nelsoni* or *thomasi*. Nevertheless, the differences in size and color, and in the skull, that separate *furvus* from *latirostris* are considerable. The most northern locality on record for *furvus* is Huechinango, Puebla, only 165 kilometers from the type locality of *latirostris*. The well-marked differences between *furvus* and *latirostris* make intergradation seem highly improbable.

Measurements.—The mean external measurements for nine adult males and four adult females are, respectively: total length, 265, 278; length of tail, 134, 143; length of hind foot, 31, 31.

Mean cranial measurements of two very old females, three old males, two old females, and six younger males, are, respectively: greatest length of skull, 36.9, 37.0, 35.8, 33.6; condylobasal length, 32.2, 32.5, 31.1,

31.0; zygomatic breadth, 18.0, 17.6, 16.9, 17.1; interorbital breadth, 5.4, 5.4, 5.3, 5.4; mastoid breadth, 14.2, 14.2, 13.8, 13.9; length of nasals, 15.6, 16.0, 15.5, 14.7; shelf of bony palate, 5.8, 6.1, 6.0, 5.7; palatine slits, 7.2, 7.3, 7.1, 7.0; diastema, 10.3, 10.1, 10.2, 9.4; post-palatal length (posterior edge of palatine slits to anterior lip of foramen magnum), 12.9, 13.1, 12.1, 12.5; length of maxillary tooth row, 5.2, 5.4, 5.1, 5.2

Specimens examined.—Total number 26, from the Xilitla region of San Luis Potosí, as follows: Xilitla, 2500 ft., 1; Apetsco, 2700 ft., 8; Cerro Miramar, 4000 ft., 3; Rancho Miramar Grande, 5000 ft., 7; Cerro Conejo, 6000 ft., 7.

NEOTOMA GOLDMANI Merriam

PYGMY WOOD RAT

Neotoma goldmani Merriam, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 16, 1903: 48. (Saltillo, Coahuila, México.)

This smallest of the known Wood Rats of this genus has previously been recorded from Saltillo and Jaral, Coahuila, by Goldman (1910: 82). There is in the collection from San Luis Potosí an adult male of this species, taken at the reservoir of the City of San Luis Potosí. It marks a considerable extension of range to the southward. Some selected external and cranial measurements of this specimen are: total length, 258; length of tail, 115; length of hind foot, 27; greatest length of skull, 37.4; condylobasal length, 35.2; basilar length, 30.5; alveolar length of maxillary tooth rows, 7.9; length of palatine slits, 8.3; zygomatic breadth, 18.7; interorbital breadth, 5.4; mastoid breadth, 13.9.

PITYMYS QUASIATER (Coues)

TROPICAL PINE MOUSE

Arvicola (Pitymys) pinetorum var. *quasiater* Coues, Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philadelphia, 1874: 191. (Jalapa, Veracruz, México.)

The Tropical Pine Mouse has previously been recorded only from central Veracruz and adjacent parts of Puebla. A series of seventeen specimens in the collection, from Apetsco, averages slightly smaller in cranial measurements than topotypes and near-topotypes. Further, the specimens from San Luis Potosí average darker in color than the large series in the United States National Museum. These latter specimens, however, have undergone post-mortem fading. E. Raymond Hall kindly compared the

specimens from San Luis Potosí with freshly taken material from Veracruz, and found no significant differences in color between the two series.

The mean measurements of five males and six females, respectively, from San Luis Potosí, each followed in parentheses by the means for the same measurements for eight males and three females from Jalapa, Jico, and Orizaba, Veracruz (specimens in United States National Museum) are: total length, 128 (127), 132 (126); length of tail, 19 (22), 20 (23); length of hind foot, 19 (17), 18 (18); greatest length of skull, 25.1 (25.6), 25.6 (25.8); length of maxillary tooth row, 6.1 (6.6), 6.3 (6.4); zygomatic breadth, 14.7 (14.9), 14.9 (15.2); interorbital breadth, 4.0 (4.0), 3.9 (4.0).

COENDOU MEXICANUM MEXICANUM (Kerr)

MEXICAN PREHENSILE-TAILED PORCUPINE

Hystrix mexicana Kerr, Anim. Kingdom, 1, 1792: 214. (Mountains of Mexico [probably in Veracruz].)

There are few published records of this mammal. The five specimens in the collection from the Xilitla Region are from the following localities: 1.5 mi. WNW Xilitla, 2; Apetsco, 1; Rancho Miramar, 1; Rancho Miramar Grande, 1. These places seem to constitute the northernmost localities from which this species is known.

CUNICULUS PACA NELSONI (Goldman)

PACA

Agouti paca nelsoni Goldman, Smithsonian Misc. Coll., no. 2, 60, 1913: 9. (Catemaco, Veracruz, México.)

This large mammal seems not to have been recorded from north of the Tuxtla Mountains of southern Veracruz. The five specimens in the present collection, all from Xilitla, include two adult females, a partial skull-only of an animal of unknown sex, the skin of an unborn fetus, and a fetus in alcohol. The series seems to be typical of *C. p. nelsoni*, and marks a considerable extension northward of the known range of the genus.

POTOS FLAVUS AZTECUS Thomas

KINKAJOU

Potos flavus aztecus Thomas, Ann. and Mag. Nat. Hist., ser. 7 (9), 1902: 268. (Atoyac, Veracruz, México.)

The skull of a young Kinkajou that was found in a cave ten kilometers north and three kilometers east of Xilitla, seems to represent the northernmost locality from which this species is known. It was previously re-

corded from northern Veracruz. Reference of the single skull to the subspecies *aztecus* is provisional, for the specimen is too young for certain identification.

GALICTES CANASTER Nelson

GRISON

Galictes canaster Nelson, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 14, 1901: 129. (Tunkas, Yucatán, México.)

This rare carnivore has been recorded from several localities in Mexico and Central America, but never from localities farther north than Orizaba, in central Veracruz. An adult female from Xilitla extends the known range of the species considerably to the northward. For the use of the generic name *Galictes*, rather than *Grison*, see Hershkovitz (1949).

CONEPATUS LEUCONOTUS TEXENSIS Merriam

COASTAL HOG-NOSED SKUNK

Conepatus leuconotus texensis Merriam, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 15, 1902: 162. (Brownsville, Cameron County, Texas.)

A young adult male of this species was taken at El Salto by the field party. It might have been expected that the specimen would most closely resemble *Conepatus leuconotus leuconotus* (Lichtenstein),¹⁰ but this did not prove to be the case. The skull is large and stout, and is like the skulls of animals taken in Texas. Merriam (1902: 162) considered the narrowing of the white band on the rump to be diagnostic of the race *texensis*. There is, however, considerable variation in this character, both in *texensis* and *leuconotus*. The specimen from El Salto has the rump band wide. Some selected cranial measurements of this specimen are: greatest length of skull, 81.6; condylobasal length, 80.3; palatal length, 35.2; post-palatal length, 38.1; length of upper tooth rows (entire), 31.7; zygomatic breadth, 48.7; interorbital breadth, 21.7; mastoid breadth, 42.3; breadth of maxillary molar rows, 31.3.

FELIS WIEDII OAXACENSIS Nelson and Goldman

LONG-TAILED TIGER CAT

Felis glauca oaxacensis Nelson and Goldman, Jour. Mamm., 12, 1931: 303. (Cerro San Felipe, near Oaxaca, Oaxaca, México.)

This rare species is known only from a few specimens from Central America and Mexico. Our specimen is an adult female from Apetsco,

¹⁰ *Mephitis leuconota* Lichtenstein, Darstellung neuer oder wenig bekannter Säugethiere, 1832: pl. 44, fig. 1. (Río Alvarado, Veracruz, México.)

near Xilitla. It differs from specimens of *Felis wiedii glaucula* Thomas¹¹ in color pattern, having the dorsal dark markings more rounded, and less elongated. In color pattern it closely resembles a specimen of *oaxacensis* from Córdoba, Veracruz. The skull of our specimen is, however, much larger than the skull of the specimen from Córdoba. Goldman (1943: 383) listed the latter specimen as an "adult, apparently female." Probably the animal is actually young, which may account for its small size. The greatest length of the skull of the type, an adult male, is given by Goldman (*loc. cit.*) as 95.7 mm. The specimen from Córdoba is only 86.1 for this same measurement. Such a great disparity in size between adult males and females of this species is not indicated by the measurements listed by Goldman, nor by specimens personally examined from Central America and Mexico. Our specimen is slightly, but not significantly, smaller than the type. The length of the maxillary tooth row (27.8) is slightly shorter than that of the type (29.4) and considerably longer than the length in the specimen from Córdoba (24.7). Some selected measurements of the specimen from San Luis Potosí are: total length, 805; length of tail, 324; length of hind foot, 106; height of ear from notch, 41; greatest length of skull, 89.7; condylobasal length, 84.3; zygomatic breadth, 60.4; braincase breadth, 42.9; interorbital breadth, 16.5; postorbital constriction, 29.2; length of maxillary tooth row, 27.8; length of upper carnassial, 10.7.

Seemingly our specimen is the third known individual of *oaxacensis*, and marks a considerable northward extension of range. No approach to *Felis wiedii cooperi* Goldman,¹² described from a single skin said to have been taken at Eagle Pass, Texas, sometime previous to 1852, is shown by our specimen. Except for the type of *cooperi*, our specimen marks the northernmost locality from which the species is known.

MAZAMA SARTORII SARTORII (Saussure)

BROCKET

C[ervus] sartorii Saussure, Revue et Magasin de Zool., ser. 2, 12, 1860: 252.
(Mirador, Veracruz, México.)

Two specimens of this little deer were obtained at Xilitla. They seem to be typical *sartorii*, which has not previously been recorded from points north of the type locality, Mirador, in central Veracruz.

¹¹ *Felis glaucula* Thomas, Ann. and Mag. Nat. Hist., ser. 7, 12, 1903: 235.
(Beltrán, Jalisco, México.)

¹² *Felis wiedii cooperi* Goldman, Jour. Mamm., 24, 1943: 384.

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